

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The article presents a comparative analysis of phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages, focusing on their translation challenges. It categorizes phraseological units into equivalents, analogs, and non-equivalent expressions, emphasizing the semantic, structural, and cultural differences between the two languages. The study highlights the importance of stylistic consistency and cultural nuance in translation, pointing out that achieving complete equivalence is often impractical. Instead, translators should strive to preserve the expressiveness and national characteristics of the source text.

Keywords: Phraseological units, idiomatic expressions, translation challenges, English and Uzbek languages, phraseological equivalents, phraseological analogs, non-equivalent phraseological units, Semantic and structural analysis.

The issues surrounding phraseology are highly significant for both practical applications and the theoretical aspects of translation; they often pose considerable practical challenges and generate strong theoretical interest due to variations in the semantic and stylistic roles that words with the same literal meaning play in different languages, as well as the differences in the combinations of these words within various languages. This paper focuses on only a few of the numerous challenges associated with the translation of phraseological units. It is commonly agreed that the equivalent of a phraseological unit should be compared to a word. However, the notion of complete equivalence is increasingly considered outdated.

This does not imply that phraseological units and words lack commonalities, as suggested by the theory exploring the correlation between certain types of phraseological units and words, which is fundamentally grounded on somewhat different principles. Phraseological expressions that consist of fixed combinations of words typically convey a meaning that is essentially equivalent to that of a single word, but they usually differ in terms of their expressive and stylistic nuances.

Certain idioms are translated through the use of partial (relative) equivalence. As noted by E. F. Arsentyeva, these idiomatic expressions display slight variations in their phraseological manifestations while sharing the same semantics, which may be componential or morphological in nature (Arsentyeva, 1989: 100). The classification of phraseological units also provides essential theoretical insight for the translator, which enables the identification of phraseological units within the text, facilitates their analysis, and allows for the most precise translation based on that analysis in the given context.

A valid method is to analyze phraseological units from three perspectives: semantic, structural grammatical, and component. Based on these identified levels, the following categories can be recognized: 1) phraseological equivalents (both full and partial) - phraseological units that share the same semantics, structural and grammatical structure, along with the same component composition.

Red book – Qizil kitob; The black prince –Qora shahzoda; Black list – Qora ro'yxat; Black diamonds – Qora oltin; Keep quiet – Sir saqlamoq; Make conversation –suhbatlashmoq; Milk cow – Sog'in sigir; First think, then speak – Avval o'yla, keyin so'yla; The dog bark, but caravan goes on – It hurar, karvon o'tar; Step by step – Qadam ba qadam.

2) phraseological analogs (full and partial) - phraseological units that express the same or similar meaning, but are characterized by a complete difference in the approximate similarity of the internal form; A black hen lays a white egg – Qora sigir oq sut berar. Cut the melon – foydanib olmoq. Put smb/smith to the test –tekshirib ko'rmoq; Red meat – Qo'y go'shti; Take a fancy to smb –Maftun bo'lmoq; Talk turkey – Ochiqdan-ochiq gapirmoq.

3) non-equivalent phraseological units- phraseological units that do not have correspondences in the phraseological system of another language. To throw up one's cap – do'ppisini osmonga otmoq. Come Yorkshire over smb –Aldamoq, nonni tuya qilmoq Betweenhawk and buzzard –Oila a'zolarini va xizmatkorlar o'rtasidagi o'rinni egallagan inson; Green room –Teatrda artistlarning kiyinadigan, yasanadigan xonasi; Harley Street – Shifokorlar, tibbiyot dunyosi (Lo'ndondagi ko'pgina mashxur doktorlar yashaydigan ko'cha); Gretna Green marriage – Uydan qochgan sevisganlar o'rtasidagi turmush;

Given that phraseology is significant for its roles in both language and communication, it necessitates a unique approach during the translation process. The primary challenge lies in the fact that no dictionary can account for all the incorrect usages of phraseology within context. Phraseological units that may appear similar in their internal structure across different languages do not always have the same meaning due to their reinterpretation, making it unwise to depend solely on the resemblance of the figurative foundation. However, when an expression continues to maintain its link to the context from which it originated, the translator must seek out equivalent phraseological units in the Uzbek language.

The way of translation in phrase -level units varies from the complete replacement of the image to the completion of the maintenance of the image in the translation. Still, it is normal, the characteristics of everyone, and the translation image is stored. But at the same time, what is standard and traditional in the source text must be conveyed in a standard and traditional way in the translation. When translating, it is important to maintain the stylistic consistency of the source text.

In addition to the absence of a corresponding phraseological unit in the Uzbek language, it may seem that the Uzbek phraseological unit, which has the same semantic content, does not correspond to the English one. Of course, the ideal would be to strive for complete equivalence of the means used, but in practice one often has to sacrifice functional and stylistic correspondence in order to preserve expressiveness. It is very important that the substitution of words in a translation conveys the national characteristics of the source language. A source text rich in idiomatic development must retain the richness and quality of that idiom.

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